

Mapping the life and memorial sites of Mikis Theodorakis

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INTRODUCTION

Mikis Theodorakis was one of the most significant Greek composers of the 20th century, achieving worldwide recognition. He also developed intense political and resistance activism both in Greece and abroad.

This project **aims to:**

- Map key milestones of his life and memorial sites.
- Highlight his international journey and global impact.
- Utilize interactive maps and multimedia to provide a vivid exploration experience of his life and work.

METHODS

RESULTS

Future improvements of the website:

- English version.
- Expanding the number of locations and adding audiovisual material.
- Structuring the platform as an educational tool on Mikis Theodorakis.
- Integration of a knowledge graph linked to map locations and biographical data.

Εξερευνήστε τους τόπους μνήμης του Μίκη Θεοδωράκη

Website content and features:

- **Web-based** multimedia platform featuring a digital map of **100 geomarkers** of life milestones and memorial sites of Mikis Theodorakis, with integrated biographical content, images and YouTube videos.
- Open-source code available on [GitHub](#) for expansion and collaboration.

Εξερευνήστε τους βασικούς σταθμούς της ζωής και του έργου του Μίκη Θεοδωράκη

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

Each geomarker documents the immense impact of Mikis Theodorakis:

- Naming of public spaces in Greece in his honor.
- International recognition through numerous awards from global organizations.
- International competitions and festivals that continue to honor his legacy to this day.

Concerts and activism abroad:

- Promotion of Greek poetry through the musical setting and presentation of works by major poets such as Ritsos, Elytis, and Seferis.
- Raising global awareness and exerting political pressure to isolate the Military Junta through high-level international contacts during the dictatorship.
- Emergence as a global symbol of unity, peace, and the protection of human rights.

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